

THE FORMATION OF VORTEX RINGS

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Technical Abstract

Vortex rings are toroidal regions of (primarily) azimuthal vorticity formed by the unsteady ejection of viscous fluid into a reservoir, through an approximately circular orifice. The boundary layer separates at the orifice in order to meet the Kutta condition at the sharp edge, and vorticity is shed into the flow in the form of a cylindrical vortex sheet. This sheet rolls up under a self-induced velocity field, forming a spiral and propagating away from the orifice.

Two aspects of the formation process are investigated: The growth of the ring, leading to a maximum circulation (where the ring ‘detaches’ from the feeding jet) and the transition between laminar and turbulent vortex rings.

Rings are generated using a piston/cylinder arrangement, feeding fluid into a reservoir of stationary fluid. Since the evolution of solitary rings is well documented, a sinusoidal perturbation is added to the velocity profile. This initiates formation of a secondary vortex, which is initially co-axial with the primary ring.

Dye flow is used for initial visualisation of turbulent breakdown and visual confirmation of results. Particle Image Velocimetry is used with a dual-camera setup to allow visualisation of the entire evolution vortex rings towards turbulence (including the well-known ‘leapfrogging’ interaction between two rings). A single camera setup is used to determine the growth of primary and secondary rings, by direct measurement of circulation.

Gharib, Rambod and Shariff (1998) demonstrate a universal timescale (or ‘Formation number,’ lying between 3.6 and 4.5) at which vortex rings achieve a maximum circulation. Contrary to expectations, it is found that the development of a secondary vortex coincides with an immediate halt to the growth of the primary ring, at a Formation number of around 1.3. It is also noted that the formation of the secondary vortex occurs at an earlier timescale than expected.

By studying the 'leapfrogging' interaction at low Reynolds numbers (then extrapolating to higher Reynolds numbers), Lim (1997) defined a model for the breakdown of vortex rings to turbulence at short timescales. A model for instability at longer timescales was already in existence (Widnall, Bliss and Tsai 1974). By performing a similar set of experiments to Lim at a higher Reynolds number, it is seen that a third mechanism for turbulent breakdown exists, which is as yet unobserved by current literature. This mechanism is brought about as a combination of the models of both Lim and Widnall.

1. Introduction

- 1.1.** Vortex rings are flow structures formed by the unsteady ejection of fluid into a reservoir, through an approximately circular orifice. Vorticity is generated at the wall boundary inside the orifice and ejected into the flow when the shear layer separates at the sharp edge of the orifice. This results in a vortex tube (or ‘cylindrical sheet’) at the interface between the jet and the stagnant fluid. The self induced velocity of the sheet then causes it to roll up into a spiral structure and propagate away from the orifice.
- 1.2.** Current literature on vortex rings encompasses many aspects of fluid mechanics including turbulence, vortex dynamics, stability analysis (linear and nonlinear) and flow-structure interaction. Study of vortex rings may therefore contribute to an improved understanding of the wider subject of fluid mechanics.
- 1.3.** From a practical perspective, vortex rings occur in nature as a method of propulsion for aquatic medusae like jellyfish (Shorten et al., 2005) as well as in the human heart (as blood is pumped from the left atrium to the ventricular cavity).
- 1.4.** This report describes an experimental investigation whereby the velocity of the feeding jet is varied sinusoidally. The result of the added perturbation is to artificially create a secondary vortex ring, with greater circulation than found in secondary rings which can occur without this excitation. The intent is to study the effect of the perturbation on two aspects of ring formation: The formation timescale of ring development and turbulent breakdown caused by the interaction (‘leapfrogging’) of the primary and secondary rings.
- 1.5.** Gharib, Rambod and Shariff (1998) indicated the existence of a universal time-scale (or ‘Formation Number’), whereby the circulation of a developing ring increases to a certain value then stays constant. The point at which maximum circulation is reached (i.e. the vortex sheet stops feeding the ring) is known as ‘Pinch-Off’. A colloquial suggestion is that the vortex ring ‘detaches’ from the sheet. In reality, the latter is misleading: Assuming continuity, the vortex sheet breaking in this way would violate Helmholtz’s first theorem (that vortex lines move with the fluid).

- 1.6.** Rosenfeld, Rambod and Gharib (1998) used a direct numerical simulation to validate the universal timescale hypothesis. Application of specific boundary conditions allowed them to show that the pinch-off point was only weakly dependant on the programme of jet velocity used. Thus we perturb the jet velocity programme to determine whether the pinch-off process is affected by the presence of a secondary vortex ring.
- 1.7.** Glezer (1988) noted that instabilities (similar to Kelvin-Helmholtz waves) develop on the vortex tube following the ring. These grow into nonlinear waves ('secondary vortex rings'). It is suggested that these disturbances lead to turbulence. Lim (1997) details the mechanism by which this occurs: Under each other's influence, the rings leapfrog. This accelerates the development of azimuthal bending waves, resulting into a breakdown to ever finer structures.
- 1.8.** Lim (1997) demonstrates a breakdown to turbulence by running simulations at low Reynolds number. By comparison with photography from Glezer (1988), Lim suggests that the vortex dynamics at high Reynolds number are similar. This study is conducted at higher Reynolds numbers with the aim of validating this suggestion.

2. Theory and Design of Experiment

2.1. Definitions

2.1.1. A number of physical parameters are used. They are summarised here. These definitions are enlarged upon in the body of the report as necessary:

Parameter	Dimensions	Description
U_p	ms^{-1}	Instantaneous velocity of piston (time dependant)
U_{mean}	ms^{-1}	Mean velocity of piston during the programme
U_{peak}	ms^{-1}	Maximum velocity reached during the cycle
A	ms^{-1}	Amplitude of perturbation
f	s^{-1} (Hz)	frequency of perturbation
L	m	Distance travelled by the piston in a certain time (based on U_{mean})
L_o	m	Stroke length of the piston (kept constant throughout) (0.4m)
D_o	m	Diameter of the cylinder (0.144m)
Γ	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	Circulation
ω_ϕ	rad.s^{-1}	Component of vorticity aligned with the azimuthal direction

Table 1 Relevant physical parameters

2.1.2. The co-ordinate system is defined as follows:

Figure 2.1 Co-ordinate system (Lim and Nickels 1995)

2.1.3. Note that the 2D nature of the measurement techniques render a fully 3D co-ordinate system unnecessary. Note also the departure from the historic convention that x is the axial direction. This is so that the x,y system is aligned with that intrinsic to the particle image velocimetry software. The circulation is the dot product of the velocity field with a line

element, evaluated around a closed line such as that indicated. If the line encloses a vortex core, circulation is useful as a measure of the strength of the vortex.

2.1.4. The circulation about the core of a vortex ring (as shown above) is equivalent to the vorticity flux through the surface bounded by that curve. This is shown by Stokes' Theorem [Equation 2-1]. In this application [3.3.2], the vorticity flux is measured taken in a planar surface passing through the axisymmetric axis of the ring (A-A). Thus, the vorticity flux measured is entirely azimuthal: The subscript is hereafter dropped from $\omega\phi$.

$$\Gamma = \int_c \mathbf{u} \cdot d\mathbf{s} = \iint_A \omega \cdot dA$$

Equation 2-1 Stokes' Theorem: The equivalence of circulation to vorticity flux

2.1.5. Rings produced under varying conditions (including but not limited to Reynolds Number) evolve according to different timescales. The parameter L/D_o is a non-dimensional timescale which allows comparison of different rings [Equation 2-2]. Gharib, Rambod and Shariff (1998) first define L/D_o as follows:

$$L/D_o = U_{\text{mean}} \cdot t / D_o \quad (\text{i})$$

where
$$U_{\text{mean}} = (1/t) \int_0^t u_p dt \quad (\text{ii})$$

and $U_p(t)$ is the instantaneous velocity of the piston [3.1.3].

Equation 2-2 Formation Timescale (Gharib, Rambod and Shariff 1998)

2.1.6. The formation timescale L/D_o should not be confused with the 'formation number' of a vortex ring, L_o/D_o , which is a value of the timescale taken at a specific point during the evolution of a given vortex ring [2.3]. Furthermore, L/D_o is based on the piston stroke distance L . There is a limit imposed on L by the equipment (the maximum value of L/D_o for which the jet can be sustained is 2.77). However, L/D_o is still valid for timescales longer than this.

2.1.7. Other dimensionless parameters are defined where relevant to the discussion, with the exception of Reynolds Number, which is based on U_{mean} and D_o except where otherwise stated.

2.2. The ‘Slug’ model

2.2.1. The ‘Slug’ model is an analytical method of predicting the circulation in a vortex ring, proposed by Maxworthy (1977). It is based on a cylindrical ‘slug’ of fluid entering the reservoir at some speed. A boundary-layer approximation allows the estimation of the vorticity which enters the flow with the slug.

$$\frac{d\Gamma_{SLUG}}{dt} = \int \omega_{\phi} u_x dr \approx \int \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial r} u_x dr \approx \int_0^{U_p(t)} \frac{\partial \left(\frac{u_x^2}{2} \right)}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{2} U_p(t)$$

Equation 2-3 Rate of change of slug circulation

$$\Gamma_{SLUG} = \int_0^T \frac{1}{2} U_p^2(t) dt$$

Equation 2-4 Slug circulation

2.2.2. Lim and Nickels (1995) give a detailed overview of the validity of the slug model, by comparison with experiment. The model is rather crude, with several effects not taken into account. The following may be particularly relevant, considering the relatively high Reynolds number of the tests (range 12600 to 39000):

2.2.2.1. At high Reynolds number, a boundary layer forms on the orifice plate, generating vorticity in the opposite sense to that in the vortex sheet [label (a), Figure 2.2]. This vorticity may enter the vortex ring, reducing the circulation compared to the prediction. This may result in regions of the ring core which consist of negative vorticity. A change in sign of the vorticity suggests instability, considering Rayleigh’s criterion for rotating flows (Maxworthy 1970).

Figure 2.2 Generation of Secondary Vorticity

2.2.3. The velocity defect in the boundary layer inside the cylinder causes the centreline velocity in the cylinder to exceed the piston velocity. This causes the slug-model to under-predict circulation at long timescales (or stroke lengths) (Lim and Nickels 1995).

2.3. 'Pinch-Off' and the Formation Number

2.3.1. The phenomenon of 'Pinch-Off' was first observed experimentally by Gharib, Rambod and Shariff (1998), hereafter referred to as 'GRS (1998)'. They showed that the circulation of a vortex ring reaches a maximum at a certain stroke length L . This was found to occur at a universal timescale:

[...] The flow field generated by large L/D_0 consists of a leading vortex ring followed by a trailing jet. The vorticity field of the leading vortex ring formed is disconnected from that of the trailing jet. On the other hand, flow fields generated by small stroke ratios show only a single vortex ring. The transition between these two distinct states is observed to occur at a stroke ratio of approximately 4, which, in this paper, is referred to as the 'formation number'.

- Gharib, Rambod and Shariff (1998)

2.3.2. Rosenfeld, Rambod and Gharib (1998) (hereafter 'RRG (1998)') confirmed the experimental findings of GRS (1998) by computational methods, directly solving the Navier-Stokes equations (DNS). The ability to set artificial boundaries allowed further investigation: Didden (1979) recognises the importance of velocity profile in the cylinder (i.e. the variation of velocity with space, across the plane of nozzle exit into the reservoir), since growth of the boundary layer at large timescales accelerates flow in the centre of the piston. This importance was confirmed, as the formation number was found to be very sensitive to changes in this profile.

2.3.3. Both GRS (1998) and RRG (1998) investigated the consequence of a non-impulsive velocity programme ($U_p = \text{fn}(t)$), see Figure 2.3. The formation number was found to rise slightly, but the dependence was weak.

Figure 2.3 Different piston velocity programmes (Gharib, Rambod and Shariff 1998)

2.3.4. The Kelvin-Benjamin variational principle is a general theorem of dynamics, which states that steady flows have maximum kinetic energy with respect to kinematically allowable perturbations (which also preserve impulse and circulation). GRS (1998) showed that the formation number corresponded with this principle (i.e. rings became steady at ‘Pinch-Off’). The correspondence was proven analytically by Mohensi and Gharib (1998).

Shusser and Gharib (1999) made the (more intuitive) argument that vortex rings pinch off when the self-induced velocity of the ring exceeds the jet velocity (taking into account the changing diameter of the jet downstream of the orifice). This was then shown to be dynamically equivalent to the condition imposed by the Kelvin-Benjamin variational principle.

2.3.5. Past work describing the pinch-off process has been conducted at Reynolds numbers an order of magnitude lower than achievable with the currently available equipment. With a Reynolds number increasing above that used by GRS (1998), several (related) effects occur:

2.3.5.1. A vortex sheet is an inviscidly unstable flow structure, with shorter wavelength perturbations stabilised by viscous action. The decreasing significance of viscous effects compared to the inertia of the flow (which characterises an increasing Reynolds number) therefore tends to make the

vortex sheet less stable (viscous effects tend to stabilise high wavenumber perturbations). This decrease in stability is closely related to the thinning of the vortex sheet at higher Re , which tends to decrease the distance over which viscosity is important (i.e. the thickness of the shear layer).

2.3.5.2. The instability of the vortex sheet is manifested in an unsteady flow developing behind the primary vortex ring. This takes the form of a varicose instability. At later times, this instability becomes non-linear: Secondary waves 'break' on the vortex sheet; these are known as secondary (and tertiary, etc.) rings [Figure 2.4]. The instability is axisymmetric, but when viewed in cross section is analogous to 2-D Kelvin-Helmholtz waves (Hammeke 1974).

Figure 2.4 Formation of 'Kelvin-Helmholtz' waves on a vortex tube, $L/D = 8$, $Re \sim 3000$ (GRS 1998)

2.3.6. Dodds (2005) investigated the effect of Re on the formation process. It was seen that the *observed* formation number decreased with Reynolds Number, according to $Re^{-0.5}$. This was explained by analogy to the jet instability regime of Becker and Massaro (1968), who studied the growth of perturbations on a continuous round jet subjected to discrete pure tones. They described a relationship between the wavelength of the growing perturbation and the Reynolds number, also according to $Re^{-0.5}$. The two experiments were related by comparing the wavelength of the perturbation to stroke length at the observed formation number.

2.3.7. There is a subtle distinction between the *observed* formation number described by Dodds and Nickels (2006) and the actual formation number as defined above (where circulation of the primary ring saturates). In Dodds and Nickels (2006), the observed formation number is based on the growth of instabilities on the feeding jet, using the hypothesis that the growth of these instabilities coincides with the actual pinch-off point. However, through

further work using D.P.I.V. techniques to measure the circulation directly, they show that this hypothesis is invalid: The circulation of the primary ring may continue to grow after the occurrence of secondary waves. Thus it is concluded that the formation number is independent of Reynolds number, although the onset of unsteadiness is not. This is reinforced by the dynamic argument of Shusser and Gharib (1999), which indicates pinch-off at $U_{\text{ring}}/U_{\text{jet}} = 1.0$. Figure 2.5 suggests that there is no significant variation of the formation number with Reynolds number.

Figure 2.5 Ring velocity ratios at varying Reynolds numbers (Dodds 2005)

2.3.8. When stating that the formation number is independent of Reynolds number, some caution must be used, since pinch-off is not entirely extricable from the occurrence of unsteadiness associated with increasing Reynolds number: Detachment (and formation of a secondary ring) is likely to affect the growth of instabilities on the sheet, as thinning of the vortex sheet takes place [2.3.5.1].

2.4. Turbulent Vortex Rings

2.4.1. A turbulent vortex ring is a toroidal region of vorticity, which is predominantly aligned with the azimuthal direction. They are characterised by a turbulent wake.

2.4.2. The formation of such rings may occur either at long timescales (where a laminar ring undergoes instability then transition) or immediately, where the vortex ring generator operates at sufficiently high Reynolds number.

Figure 2.6 Stages in turbulent breakdown due to azimuthal instability. A laminar ring forms in frames (a) to (c). Instability is first seen in frame (d) before its manifestation in frame (e). The ring abruptly becomes fully turbulent in (f). (Didden 1977)

2.4.3. An intermediate region exists, where a laminar ring breaks down to turbulence within the range of experimental observation. Experimental study of this region should yield clearer understanding of the mechanism which causes breakdown.

2.4.4. Widnall and Sullivan (1973) define the instability which leads to turbulence in a single ring: It is shown analytically and experimentally that azimuthal waves develop around the core of a vortex ring (of small but finite core size). The distribution of vorticity (i.e. the core size) is found to influence the number of waves in the mode. Widnall, Bliss and Tsai (1974) formulate this instability by consideration of the Crow instability (Crow 1970). This addresses the appearance of bending-waves on a vortex pair, and can be applied to vortex rings, with diametrically opposite sides of the ring acting as a vortex pair [Figure 2.7].

Figure 2.7 a. Short wavelength instability of a vortex pair (Leweke and Williamson 1996) and b. Analogy of this instability to a vortex ring (Widnall, Bliss and Tsai 1974)

2.4.5. The ‘Widnall Instability’ on a solitary ring typically evolves over longer timescales than visible with the equipment in use, although the initial formation of azimuthal bending waves has been seen with the current apparatus [Figure 2.8]. Maxworthy (1977) notes that onset and breakdown of the azimuthal core instability occurs closer to the orifice for increasing Reynolds number of an initially laminar ring.

Figure 2.8 Azimuthal instability, photographed from above to visualise three-dimensionality ($Re \sim 6000$, $L/D_o \sim 10$)

2.4.6. Glezer (1988) offers an alternative explanation for the immediate transition to turbulence. Using high-speed cinephotography, the appearance of Kelvin-Helmholtz waves on the vortex sheet are noted, and the comment is made that the initial instability wavelength is likely decrease with increasing exit velocity. This is in accord with the reasoning in section [2.3.5.1].

2.4.7. Glezer makes the conjecture that the ‘Kelvin-Helmholtz’ disturbances accelerate the onset of the azimuthal instability, its amplification and the subsequent breakdown to turbulence.

2.4.8. Lim (1997) conducts an experimental investigation into the role of the Kelvin-Helmholtz-like instability in the formation of turbulent vortex rings:

“[...] it is shown through a systematic experimental investigation that although the Kelvin-Helmholtz-like instability plays an important role in initiating the transition process, it is the leapfrogging phenomenon between the primary and secondary vortex rings which is responsible for hastening the development of azimuthal bending waves”

(from the abstract, Lim 1997)

2.4.9. The self induced velocity of two co-axial vortex rings (turbulent or laminar) causes them to alternately pass through one another. This process is called leapfrogging, and is best described by visualisation [Figure 2.9]. Note the increasing misalignment of the rings as time increases (left to right):

Figure 2.9 Leapfrogging of two vortex rings (Yamada and Matsui 1978)

2.4.10. It is observed that primary and secondary rings become misaligned during the leapfrogging process. When the axial directions of the primary and secondary rings are not collinear, the leapfrogging process becomes three-dimensional (as opposed to two-dimensional axisymmetric), with different parts of each ring leapfrogging at different times. The vortex filaments become entangled, generating fine-scale turbulent structures.

2.4.11. Lim notes that, during leapfrogging, the primary and secondary rings develop an azimuthal instability greater than observed in an isolated ring at the same timescale. This makes intuitive sense, since a second vortex ring increases the ‘pairing’ (Crow 1970). However, emphasis is placed on the misalignment of the rings as a mechanism of breakdown.

3. Apparatus and experimental techniques

3.1. Apparatus

3.1.1. Experimental work was conducted in the Cambridge University Engineering Department Hydraulics Laboratory, using a rig dedicated to the study of vortex rings.

3.1.2. The water tank (measuring 700 x 700 x 1500 mm high) contains the reservoir of stationary water. Fitted to the top is a piston/cylinder arrangement in a vertical orientation, with an orifice plate in the horizontal plane [indicated in

Figure 3.1 Experimental apparatus

3.1.3. The piston is driven by an integrated stepper motor and controller, via a ballscrew rotary-to-linear converter. Basic programs are developed and run from a remote PC control the piston motion. The piston velocity programme is set by a number of parameters; stroke length L_0 (m), mean velocity U_{mean} (ms^{-1}) perturbation frequency f (s^{-1}) and perturbation amplitude A (m) [see Figure 3.2]. The maximum velocity occurring during the cycle is referred to as U_{peak} (ms^{-1}) ($U_{\text{peak}} = 2\pi.f.A + U_{\text{mean}}$).

Figure 3.2 Piston velocity programme

3.1.4. Accuracy of the piston motion was verified using a rotary potentiometer and oscilloscope. Mean velocity was found to be accurate to within $1\text{mm}\text{s}^{-1}$, in accordance with a previous calibration (Dodds 2005). An upper bound exists on the frequency or amplitude: Increasing either of these causes a proportional increase in U_{peak} . If this violates the internal limit to velocity in the motor controller, the programme is automatically halted. For the required perturbation size ($2.\pi.A.F < U_{\text{mean}}$, to avoid negative piston/jet velocity), this bound was not exceeded. In testing, a flat frequency response was found across the range necessary (up to 1.5 Hz); i.e. inertial effects of the piston and water did not prevent the piston achieving the requested velocity.

3.2. Flow Visualisation - Dye

- 3.2.1. Rhodamine dye was injected into the flow at the point of separation where the jet issues into the stagnant flow [
- 3.2.2.
- 3.2.3. Figure 3.1]. These diametrically opposed nozzles were gravity fed from a separate reservoir, via a control valve. The dye is advected with the flow and gives a 2-D visualisation of the evolution of the shear layer.
- 3.2.4. Despite clearly showing the evolution of the vortex ring, dye flow visualisation has limitations: Ring circulation cannot be measured directly, although it may be estimated using the 'slug' model [2.2]. Furthermore, despite being added at the point where vorticity enters the flow, dye cannot be used to determine the distribution of vorticity [3.2.5, 3.2.6].
- 3.2.5. The Schmidt Number (approx 1000 for Rhodamine dye in water) indicates the rate of diffusion of vorticity relative to the rate of diffusion of dye. In this case, then, vorticity diffuses around 1000 times faster than the scalar dye: Dye cannot be used to measure the thickness of the shear layer (with the academic exception of an extremely high Reynolds number flow, where diffusion of either vorticity or the scalar dye may be considered negligible).
- 3.2.6. The transport equation for vorticity contains a term representing the intensification of vorticity by stretching a vortex line. Conservation of the scalar mass ensures that there is no such analogous term in the scalar transport equation. Thus where there is a distortion of the vortex ring in a three-dimensional velocity field (such as the leapfrogging of misaligned vortex rings), dye-flow may not provide an appropriate visualisation.

3.3. Digital Particle Image Velocimetry

3.3.1. Particle image velocimetry was conducted using a Pegasus – New Wave 527nm Class IV ND-YLF laser, and LaVision’s ‘DaVis’ software. Cameras were ‘High-Speedstar 4’ models supplied by LaVision, using standard 50 mm Nikon lenses.

3.3.2. The laser fan was oriented vertically in the tank, intersecting with the axis of the cylinder and normal to the camera arrangement [Figure 3.3]. A trial was made with a wide-angle lens, but poor image quality led to erroneous results. Instead a dual camera setup was used to extend the field of view downwards, thereby capturing the entire evolution of leapfrogging rings [Figure 3.4]. The dual-camera setup had not been attempted in the past in this laboratory; there was little past experience to draw on.

Figure 3.3 2D General Arrangement of PIV apparatus (not to scale)

Figure 3.4 Extension of field of view using two cameras (LaVision Flowmaster 7.0 Software manual)

3.3.3. Note that the dual camera setup was used ‘over-and-under’ rather than in the ‘side-by-side’ arrangement suggested by Figure 3.4. The fields of view were overlapped (by approximately 5cm) to provide a continuous measurement.

3.3.4. The seeding particles used were Dantec 250µm hollow glass, of (approximately) neutral bouyancy and with reflective silver oxide coating. The amount of seeding used varied throughout the testing, reducing with increased frame rate and increasing with Reynolds number.

3.3.5. Images were processed as according to directions in the LaVision Flow-Master User Manual. The best results were found using a multiple-pass approach, with window size decreasing from 64 to 16 pixels (both with 25% overlap). Image pre-processing included the subtraction of a base image (the first in the series of frames) and particle intensity normalisation (with a 10 pixel scale length).

3.3.6. Measurements of the circulation were taken directly from the LaVision ‘DaVis’ software. Once the vorticity distribution had been calculated, regions were selected to include the entire vortex core [Figure 3.5], whilst avoiding spurious data (often seen at the edge of the laser sheet). The average vorticity flux through the defined rectangle was output from the software. Multiplying this by the area of the rectangle gave the total vorticity flux through the surface enclosed by the rectangle, which is equivalent to the circulation of the ring [2.1.4]. Consideration of Stokes’ Theorem (relating circulation to vorticity flux) indicates

that any size or shape region is acceptable provided it fully encloses the core of the vortex [2.1.4]. Dodds (2005) verified this experimentally, using the same apparatus as this experiment.

Figure 3.5 A typical PIV plot of a vortex ring (velocity vectors superimposed on vorticity plot).

Note the rectangle used to calculate the vorticity flux.

3.3.7. There are four notable sources of error usually associated with this technique:

3.3.7.1. Numerical error. The continuous vorticity field is discretised into small ‘windows’. This source of error may be reduced by reducing the window size (down to a limit imposed by the density of seeding). Typically, this error is negligible in comparison to other sources.

3.3.7.2. Background vorticity. Testing in rapid succession may mean that vorticity from a previous test may still be present in the flow. This is mitigated by waiting approx 30 minutes between each test (the amount of time required to load data from the previous test and back it up).

3.3.7.3. Spurious data. The edge of the laser sheet, as well as poorly matched seeding, may cause erroneous velocity vectors. This in turn translates to ‘noise’ in the vector field. To mitigate this (if necessary), background (‘no-flow’) readings may be taken of the noise in each vector field. Averaging the RMS value of this noise will give an idea of the magnitude of the error, and results can be filtered accordingly.

3.3.7.4. Defined regions which do not encompass the entire core. Where rings are close together, it is difficult to define rectangular regions which encompass the whole of one ring, and none of the other.

3.3.8. The following commentary on accuracy of the results achieved is included here, for the sake of clarity in the 'Results and Discussion' section.

3.3.9. In the event, the PIV visualisation was flawed. A problem with scaling caused solutions for some fields of view to be significantly weaker than others. Despite discussion with the LaVision Applications Consultant, the problem was irreparable. There are several aspects to consider when mitigating this large source of inaccuracy:

3.3.9.1. Measurements of circulation are scaled by some constant. This constant is clearly the same for some tests, but not for others. Being unable to ascertain which tests have the correct constant and which do not renders direct comparison with results from other sources difficult.

3.3.9.2. Those tests which have the same constant may be compared to each other. This is the method used to draw conclusions (so long as the conclusion is not based on measured absolute values of circulation). Scaling the results by the ratio between the slug model prediction for that test and the peak circulation found during the test may allow comparison with other sources, although the crude nature of the slug model (Lim and Nickels 1995) indicates that this approach is likely to be unreliable.

3.3.9.3. Since the pinch-off process occurs entirely within the field of view of the upper camera, measurements of circulation for comparison between tests were based only on results from camera 1. Thus, differences between the scaling of each camera would not affect the results as the ring passes between the two fields of view.

3.3.9.4. It is possible to see the development of the rings across both fields of view in all cases, so qualitative observations can be made. In only a few tests (all three perturbed cases at $Re = 25200$, two perturbed cases at $Re = 19000$, and a few occasional cases at other Re) were the results from both cameras scaled by the same amount. Quantitative measurements may only be made for these cases. This, however, is not particularly restrictive: Measurements in two dimensions are insufficient to fully describe the three dimensional nature of turbulence - the original intent was to make a qualitative study of the motion, which is achievable even with faint vector fields.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Overview

- 4.1.1. The following discussion intends to address two separate issues; the effect of a frequency perturbation on the pinch-off process and the transition of vortex rings to turbulence by leapfrogging [2.3, 2.4]. A range of Re and perturbation amplitudes have been tested, using the PIV techniques discussed in section [3.3].
- 4.1.2. Analysis is complicated by the varying levels of intensity brought about by the problem discussed above [3.3.9]. In the case of the pinch-off process, the formation of both rings is encompassed by the field of view of the first camera. Quantitative results describing pinch-off may be compared between tests (measurements are based on images from the first camera only). When considering the breakdown to turbulence over a longer time period, a more qualitative approach has been taken. The use of the incorrectly scaled vector fields can be justified for flow visualisation (position of the vortex rings remains unaffected). Enough good quality results spanning both fields have been produced to measure the variation of circulation during the merging of two rings. It is also possible to compare the vortex core sizes between tests.
- 4.1.3. Also relevant to both processes is the choice of frequency used during the testing. For each test case, the frequency has been chosen to fit two complete cycles to the duration of the stroke ($N_{cyc} = 2$). For the investigation of pinch-off, it was unnecessary to produce more than two rings. In the investigation of turbulent breakdown, a reduction in the number of rings vastly reduces the complexity of the flow-field. This in turn allows clearer visualisation and interpretation of the interaction between the rings. Note that Lim (1997) uses up to three rings, but at a lower Reynolds number than used here (implying a slower transition to turbulence – using this equipment to produce several rings in quick succession produces a breakdown very close to the nozzle which is rather more difficult to study. The amplitude of the perturbation would also be limited prohibitively [3.1.4]).
- 4.1.4. Whole cycles were used (rather than, say, one and a half cycles, which would also produce a secondary ring) in an attempt to ensure that both rings had a similar distribution of vorticity.

4.1.5. At this point, it is worth mentioning the parameter used to nondimensionalise the circulation (on those graphs which are able to be plotted satisfactorily). Conventionally, the parameter has been:

$$\text{Nondimensional circulation} = \Gamma / U_{\text{mean}} \cdot D_o$$

This was found to be unsatisfactory, as the peak value of the circulation varied with the amplitude of the perturbation. Instead, the peak velocity of the piston (U_{peak}) was used:

$$\text{Nondimensional circulation} = \Gamma / U_{\text{peak}} \cdot D_o$$

This allowed a more satisfactory comparison between results.

4.1.6. It is mentioned in section [3.3.9] that the slug circulation may be used to scale plots further, mitigating the differences in intensity between different tests. Ultimately this was unnecessary since enough tests with the same scaling were found to complete the analysis.

4.2. The effect of perturbation on Pinch-Off:

4.2.1. Figure 4.1 shows a series of images of a single forming vortex ring (i.e. without perturbation), visualised using a vorticity plot extracted from the PIV data. These images document the formation of a single ring which is used as a control comparison later.

Figure 4.1 Cross sectional vorticity plot showing stages of ring formation.

4.2.2. Figure 4.1 (a) shows the first roll-up of the vortex ring, very early on in development. The vortex sheet seen in (b) feeds the ring until the Formation number is reached ('pinch-off'). By $L/D_0 = 2.9$, waves have formed on the feeding sheet (c), although circulation of the primary ring continues to increase. At $L/D_0 = 3.9$ (d) the primary ring seems to detach

from the feeding sheet ('pinch-off'). It is at this point that the circulation begins to saturate [Figure 4.3]. The waves (which have also grown in circulation) evolve into an unsteady wake; a 'train' of vortex rings following the primary. These will later interact with the primary ring, leapfrogging in the manner described in [2.4.9].

4.2.3. The above visualisation of ring formation is consistent with past studies, notably the numeric work of Rosenfeld, Rambod and Gharib (1998). Figure 4.2 directly illustrates the relationship between formation timescale and the velocity distribution. Annotations accord to those in Figure 4.1, although no secondary waves (c) form in the DNS solution (it is at a lower Reynolds number than the PIV simulation above).

**Figure 4.2 Evolution of ring circulation with vorticity distributions calculated by DNS
(Rosenfeld, Rambod and Gharib 1998)**

4.2.4. Figure 4.3 reveals the key finding of this experiment. For a particular Reynolds number, it shows the development of primary and secondary rings created in four tests, with varying amplitudes. Refer to Figure 3.2 for the velocity programme taken by the piston (in terms of formation number).

Figure 4.3 Variation of nondimensional circulation with amplitude (tests at $Re = 12600$)

4.2.5. The line indicating the development of the 'control' ring (i.e. that resulting from an unperturbed velocity programme) shows a saturation of circulation in the region $3.5 < L/D_0 < 4.5$, consistent with current theory [2.3.1].

4.2.6. However, rings formed with perturbed programmes show clear deviation from this behaviour: The deceleration of the piston after the first cycle coincides with rapid (or ‘artificial’) pinch-off of the primary ring, at $L/D_0 \sim 1.3$. Thereafter, vorticity is subsumed into the secondary ring. This observation contradicts past studies (notably Gharib, Rambod and Shariff (1998) and Rosenfeld, Rambod and Gharib (1998)), which conclude that the velocity programme has a weak influence on the formation number.

4.2.7. A further significant point is that the secondary ring does not form as the piston accelerates during the second cycle (as is intuitively expected), but during deceleration from the first cycle.

4.2.8. An initial thought is that this artificial pinch-off is related to the dynamic theorem (Shusser and Gharib (1999) and para. 2.3.4) that a ring pinches off when ring velocity exceeds that of the jet.

4.2.9. However, the rapidity of the pinch-off suggests that more than just the dynamic theory is at play: In the control experiment, the piston slowed and stopped at a formation time of 2.7. After this point, the circulation of the ring continued to increase before saturating. If an analogy were to be drawn, it would be expected that the primary ring would continue to increase in circulation after formation of the secondary ring. This would accord with the observations of Dodds (2005), where circulation of a primary ring continued to increase after the formation of secondary instabilities.

4.2.10. Unsteadiness of the feeding jet is not taken into account by the dynamic theorem, and so caution must be used when considering its relevance. An adjusted equivalent must exist for unsteady flow.

4.2.11. Make the assumption that the slug model realistically predicts the circulation contained in the primary ring. According to the slug model [Equation 2-1], the rate of change of circulation is proportional to $U_p = -2.\pi.A.f.\cos(2.\pi.f.t) + U_{mean}$. Differentiating further shows that $d^2\Gamma/dt^2$ is proportional to the acceleration of the piston.

$$\frac{d\Gamma_{SLUG}}{dt} = \int \omega_{\phi} u_x dr \approx \int \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial r} u_x dr \approx \int_0^{U_p(t)} \frac{\partial \left(\frac{u_x^2}{2} \right)}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{2} U_p(t)$$

Equation 2-3 Rate of change of slug circulation

In the course of the $\frac{1}{4}$ cycle where $1.0 < L/D_0 < 1.4$ [Figure 4.3], the acceleration of the piston takes a large jump from positive to negative. This ‘step’ decrease in $d^2\Gamma/dt^2$ accounts for the sharp change in gradient of the circulation curve for the primary ring during this time interval, although does not directly indicate pinch-off.

4.2.12. Deceleration of the piston results in a thinning of the existing vortex sheet (the increase in jet velocity in the axial direction acts to ‘stretch’ the sheet). This also occurs in the control case as the piston reaches maximum stroke. In the perturbed case, however, the piston continues to feed the flow. The thin region of the vortex sheet thus convects away from the orifice and, being less stable than a thicker sheet, tends to roll up into a secondary vortex.

4.2.13. Consider the conservation of vorticity: We neglect small disturbances, diffusion and remnants of vorticity within the extremely thin vortex sheet connecting the rings [1.5]. The assumption that no ‘Kelvin-Helmholtz’ waves have developed naturally (i.e. with a different wavenumber to the excited rings) is also made (this assumption is verified using PIV plots of vorticity). Making the above assumptions, all vorticity must enter one of the two vortex rings. It is therefore unsurprising that the total (nondimensional) circulation of the secondary and primary rings coincides with the total (nondimensional) circulation of a single ring produced with the same stroke length and Reynolds number.

4.2.14. The artificially forced pinch-off point always occurs at the same formation number (~ 1.3). For a range of perturbations (at a constant Reynolds number), then, the circulation of the primary ring (Γ_1) remains constant. It follows that since the total circulation is constant for tests of different perturbation amplitude, the circulation of the secondary ring (Γ_2) and the ratio between ring circulations (Γ_2/Γ_1) should both remain constant. Figure 4.3 reinforces this.

4.3. Transition to turbulence

Figure 4.4 a. PIV visualisation - different paths to turbulence

4.3.1. Frames 1 and 2 show normal leapfrogging. In frames 3,4 and 5, leapfrogging continues, but the secondary ring is turbulent. Frames 6 and 7 show the ingestion of the turbulent secondary ring into the primary, while frame 8 shows the resultant single turbulent ring.

Figure 4.4 b. PIV visualisation – different paths to turbulence

4.3.2. The entire series shows normal leapfrogging, with a particularly large misalignment in the later stages. The rings in frames 2 and 3 are doubled slightly, this is an effect caused by slight misalignment of the overlapping camera fields rather than a feature of the flow.

4.3.3. Figure 4.5 was taken at a Reynolds number of 25200. Series (a) was taken with a perturbation amplitude $A = 10$ mm. Series B was taken with a perturbation amplitude $A = 20$ mm.

4.3.4. The next logical step is to document the variation of circulation during the merging process, [Figure 4.5].

Figure 4.5 Circulation of vortex rings during the merging process

4.3.5. Key features of Figure 4.5 include:

4.3.5.1. Coalescence of the two rings into one is shown. By the principle of conservation of vorticity discussed in [4.2.13] the total circulation when merged should approximate the total circulation before the merge takes place. This is confirmed approximately (a).

4.3.5.2. Circulation is measured in the 2-D plane of the laser sheet, so only accounts for the azimuthal component of vorticity flux. As a ring breaks down to turbulence, vorticity in the flow is no longer entirely aligned with the azimuthal direction. Thus, since total vorticity is conserved, the breakdown to turbulence of a ring should coincide with a sharp decrease in measured circulation. This is observed in region (b), coinciding with the formation number at which the

secondary ring is seen to turn turbulent [Figure 4.6]. Note that the still-laminar primary ring does not decrease in circulation.

4.3.5.3. A particularly noisy region is labelled (c). This noise is produced by poorly defined regions for calculation of vorticity flux: As rings move close together and merge, it becomes impossible to define a clear boundary between the two, as discussed in [3.3.7.4].

Figure 4.6 a. Secondary ring turns turbulent at the point of leapfrogging, $A = 10\text{mm}$
b. Secondary ring leapfrogs successfully, $A = 20\text{mm}$

4.3.6. In summary of current theory, it is recognised that a laminar vortex ring (at low Reynolds numbers) eventually undergoes the Widnall instability and breaks down to turbulence. At higher Reynolds numbers, where turbulence occurs almost instantaneously, Lim (1997) proposes that secondary rings formed from the Kelvin-Helmholtz-like instability leapfrog the primary ring, resulting in the vortex filaments becoming entangled due to misalignment during leapfrogging. This leads to turbulence.

4.3.7. However, in the light of the two different progressions identified by Figure 4.5, it is reasonable to suppose that a third effect is at play. Figure 4.6 shows the dye flow visualisation of the experiment in Figure 4.5.

4.3.8. This visualisation offers some clues: In (a), turbulence is not caused by the leapfrogging/misalignment mechanism observed in (b). The following sequence describes the development of flow (a) to turbulence:

4.3.8.1. Both rings initially exhibit a small azimuthal instability (seen as ‘waviness’ in the dye).

4.3.8.2. As the secondary ring passes through the centre of the primary (during the first leapfrog), it suddenly turns turbulent, while the primary ring remains mostly laminar (still exhibiting the azimuthal ‘waviness’, but otherwise unchanged).

4.3.8.3. The leapfrogging process continues, but is cut short as the turbulent secondary ring is ingested into the primary, causing complete breakdown.

4.3.9. Two (dependant) questions remain:

4.3.9.1. Why does the secondary ring of flow (a) turn so rapidly turbulent?

4.3.9.2. Why does the secondary ring in flow (a) turn turbulent when the secondary ring in flow (b) does not?

4.3.10. It could be argued that the secondary ring trips to turbulence independently, by ingestion of Kelvin-Helmholtz waves and leapfrogging as described by Lim. Three observations contradict this:

4.3.10.1. Dye flow shows no sign of significant Kelvin-Helmholtz-like patterns emerging.

4.3.10.2. Immediately before the leapfrogging takes place, the secondary ring is almost laminar (apart from slight azimuthal instability) and shows no signs of imminent breakdown.

4.3.10.3. The phenomenon was observed with the test repeated across a range of Reynolds numbers, keeping the perturbation amplitude constant.

4.3.11. For the Widnall Instability, the amplification rate of sinusoidal perturbations is given as:

$$\alpha \approx (\Gamma/4\pi R^2)n\sqrt{1-n^2}.\ln(a/R)$$

Equation 4-1 Amplification rate of the Widnall instability

(eqn 35, Widnall and Sullivan 1973)

i.e., it has a clear dependence on R, the ring radius [2.1.2]. As the secondary ring decreases in radius during the leapfrogging process, the amplification rate of any azimuthal instability increases rapidly. ‘n’ is the wavenumber of the instability, an integer typically much greater than 1 for the rings considered here. ‘a’ is the core diameter.

4.3.12. If the amplification of the instability in the secondary ring is sufficient, the ring will break down to turbulence. Given that the maximum amplification rate of instabilities is at the point of minimum radius, the breakdown is most likely to occur at or shortly after it passes through the point of maximum diameter.

4.3.13. The above offers a satisfactory explanation for the cause of the breakdown; but does not rigorously explain why the process is dependant on the amplitude of the perturbation made in the velocity programme.

4.3.14. To demonstrate the dependence on perturbation size, we return to the abstract of Widnall and Sullivan (1973) and see that:

“The number of waves [n] around the perimeter in the unstable mode depends on the size of the vortex core.

For a given vortex core, only one mode is unstable, and the smaller the vortex core, the larger the number of waves in the mode.”

(from abstract, Widnall and Sullivan 1973)

Noting that the a/R ratio of the vortex rings we consider is typically in the range $0.35 < a/R < 0.77$ (and is always less than 1), the $\ln(a/R)$ term in Equation 4-1 will always be negative. Since n is at least three for unstable modes, and typically much greater, the amplification rate scales approximately with n^2 . Since n scales inversely to core size (see extract above), it is seen that a ring with smaller core size will be subject to a greater amplification rate than a ring with a larger core diameter.

4.3.15. Applying this to the data seen in Figure 4.4 (a) and (b), it is reasonable to suppose that were the secondary ring in (a) to have a significantly smaller core size than that in (b), the comparative increase in amplification rate could cause turbulent breakdown in case (a), whilst case (b) remains laminar.

4.3.16. With all other parameters held constant, Figure 4.7 indicates the variance in core sizes with perturbation amplitude for cases (a) and (b) from Figure 4.4, and a case (c), representing still larger perturbation at the same Reynolds number. The visualisation shows that the secondary core size *does* increase with increasing perturbation size, in accordance with [4.3.13].

Figure 4.7 Variance of secondary ring core size with perturbation amplitude

- 4.3.17. The circulation Γ_2 of the secondary ring decreases with decreasing perturbation amplitude. The amplification rate of the azimuthal instability is proportional to ring circulation. The square relationship between increasing amplification rate and wavenumber is dominant over the decrease due to reduced circulation. Note that an additional stabilising effect is the increase in core size with decreasing radius R , by virtue of the vortex stretching term in the vorticity transport equation.
- 4.3.18. Although it was difficult to capture in focus, when operating the piston in the upper range of Reynolds numbers (~ 38000 , where the ring turns turbulent immediately) a series of very high wavenumber ‘Kelvin-Helmholtz’ instabilities are seen in the vortex sheet. This corresponds to the discussion of vortex sheet instability in section [2.3.5.1], and the observations of Glezer (1988).
- 4.3.19. It is worthwhile noting that once a secondary ring (of finite core size) enters the flow, the profile of induced velocity between it and the primary ring (also of finite core size) will always consist of two inflexion points, and is therefore unstable according to Rayleigh’s criterion for rotating flows. This observation warrants further investigation.

5. Conclusions

5.1. The Formation Process - Observations

- 5.1.1. Contradictory to observations in the current literature, it has been seen that the formation number may be heavily dependant on the shape of the piston velocity programme. In this case, a formation number of ~ 1.3 was seen; a factor of three less than the formation number previously thought universal.
- 5.1.2. The presence of a strong secondary ring affects the formation number in a way that 'Kelvin-Helmholtz' instabilities do not (Dodds and Nickels (2005) conclude that the formation number is independent of Reynolds number, despite the appearance of secondary instabilities.
- 5.1.3. Once a perturbation is large enough to cause pinch-off from the primary jet, significant increases in the size of the perturbation have only a weak effect on the relative circulation of the primary to the secondary ring.

5.2. The Formation Process -Recommendations

- 5.2.1. To understand the mechanism of pinch-off at this new, low formation number, it is necessary to have correctly scaled readings of circulation and velocity. If this were the case, the ring velocities could be plotted in a similar fashion to Figure 2.5, thereby testing whether the dynamic theorem of formation (Shusser and Gharib 1999) is applicable to this flow. Corrections may have to be made for the unsteady nature of the jet velocity.
- 5.2.2. The most informative action would be to traverse a finer range of amplitudes, perhaps just at a single Reynolds number (the number of amplitudes tested was limited in this series, in order to increase the range of Reynolds number tested). A transition point must exist (at some value of amplitude) for which the conventional formation process takes over. It is possible that observing behaviour around this transition point will provide a source of information about the jet instability regime (Dodds 2005).

5.3. Breakdown to Turbulence – Observations

- 5.3.1. Testing at a higher Reynolds number than Lim (1997) allowed a more detailed observation of the breakdown to turbulence at short timescales. It is shown that secondary rings (which can be extrapolated to include ‘Kelvin-Helmholtz’ instabilities) undergoing leapfrogging become significantly more vulnerable to the Widnall instability, which is amplified during the leapfrogging process. If amplified sufficiently, the secondary ring breaks rapidly to turbulence. It is then ingested into the primary ring before further leapfrogging can occur. The presence of a fully turbulent region in the primary ring rapidly turns the primary ring turbulent. This is an effect unseen to date, and not mentioned in the relevant literature.
- 5.3.2. Where conditions are not conducive to a turbulent breakdown as described above, it is found that pairs of rings generated at high Reynolds number do indeed follow the breakdown to turbulence due to misalignment while leapfrogging observed by Lim (1997).

Breakdown to Turbulence – Recommendations

- 5.3.3. It is noted that the distribution of velocity between pairs of rings is always unstable according to the Rayleigh Criterion for rotating flows. Outside the scope of the current work, this instability would be worth investigation.
- 5.3.4. The study made of turbulent breakdown is largely qualitative; by virtue of the 2-D nature of the measurement technique used. Either fully 3-D or stereoscopic PIV would allow quantification of the out-of plane velocities indicative of turbulence.
- 5.3.5. Re-setting the equipment to prevent the intensity problems would allow direct measurements of core sizes and circulations to take place. Thus, the rate of amplification of the Widnall instability could be found throughout the leapfrog cycle, and numerically integrated to give a value of the instability amplitude as a function of time. If experiments take place across a finer range of perturbation amplitudes, comparison with the threshold value of instability amplitude required for rapid turbulent breakdown, and a more concrete relationship could be derived.

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